

Final Report for the DFG Project

SINIR – Simulating INteractive Information Retrieval

Timo Borst, Michael Granitzer, Sebastian Günther, Matthias Hagen, Kim Plassmeier, Klaus
Tochtermann, Saber Zerhoudi

January 25, 2024

Project Identifier (DFG-Geschäftszeichen)

HA 5851/3-1

Project Number

408022022

Applicants

Prof. Dr. Matthias Hagen

Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena (FSU) (project started at Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg (MLU))

Prof. Dr. Michael Granitzer

University of Passau (UP)

Prof. Dr. Klaus Tochtermann

Leibniz-Informationszentrum Wirtschaft (ZBW)

Project Title

SINIR – Simulating INteractive Information Retrieval

Reporting Period

November 1, 2019 — August 31, 2023

2 Summary

We have developed models and frameworks for simulating user interactions and search behavior in digital libraries, with a particular focus on query modification and search result navigation. As a starting point, we analyzed and categorized types of user behavior in search logs [PR1, PR2] to then inform generalized models—including a first-order Markov model, a contextual Markov model, and a time-aware Markov model—that emulate the general user behavior from training datasets [PR1], as well as more nuanced, user-type specific interactions that provide deeper insights into user search sessions [PR2].

Our first-order Markov model realistically reflects how searchers modify queries and engage with search results [PR3] with a simulation accuracy exceeding that of previous methods [PR4]. Still, we could achieve further improvements for detailed simulations by using a contextual Markov model [PR3], which takes into account a range of user behavior and contextual nuances, resulting in highly accurate simulations. We have also demonstrated that LSTM-based simulation is promising [PR5].

Our models' simulated sessions provide a comprehensive representation of user interactions [PR4] and effectively mimic human query modifications and result exploration [PR6]. We have introduced a probabilistic approach to understand search result engagement, which helps to determine the importance of each interaction. Continuing after the project, we are currently developing a simulation method based on generative adversarial networks (GANs), conditioned on query changes and the dynamics of search sessions.

As for user interactions, we have studied how queries are modified and how search results are navigated in interactive sessions [PR4, PR7]. We have used embedding space alignment to bridge between corpora, allowing a combination of interaction and evaluation data. Finally, we released the open-source SimIIR 2.0 framework that provides a detailed toolset for searcher simulation [PR6]. Based on user behavior models, the framework ensures that the simulations are realistic, coherent, and free from inconsistencies.

Zusammenfassung

Wir haben Modelle und ein Framework zur Simulation von Benutzerinteraktionen und Suchverhalten im Bereich digitaler Bibliotheken entwickelt. Schwerpunkte waren das (Re-)Formulieren von Suchanfragen und die Interaktion mit den Suchergebnissen. Als Ausgangspunkt haben wir zunächst das Nutzerverhalten in Such-Logs analysiert und kategorisiert, z.B. in explorative Suche und Known-Item-Suche [PR1, PR2]. Im Anschluss haben wir Modelle entwickelt – bspw. ein Markov-Modell erster Ordnung, ein kontextabhängiges Markov-Modell und ein zeitabhängiges Markov-Modell –, die das in Such-Logs beobachtete Verhalten emulieren und simulieren können [PR2].

Unsere Modelle sollen möglichst realistisch nachbilden, wie Benutzer mit Suchergebnissen interagieren und Suchanfragen ändern [PR3]. Die Genauigkeit unserer Simulationen ist besser als die vorheriger Methoden, da unsere ausgefeilteren Modelle, wie etwa das kontextabhängige Markov-Modell, variierendes Nutzerverhalten und kontextuelle Nuancen berücksichtigen [PR3]. Außerdem konnten wir zeigen, dass auch LSTM-basierte Simulation von Benutzerinteraktionen vielversprechend ist [PR5].

Unsere entwickelten Modelle simulieren Suchsitzungen, die ein weites Spektrum von Benutzerinteraktionen umfassen [PR4], insbesondere auch, wie Benutzer Suchanfragen ändern und die Ergebnisse betrachten [PR6]. Wir haben einen probabilistischen Ansatz genutzt, um zu verstehen, wie Nutzer mit Suchergebnissen interagieren und was die Bedeutung einzelner Interaktionen ist. Nach Projektabschluss entwickeln wir derzeit noch eine weitere Methode zur Simulation von Suchverhalten mit Hilfe von generativen Adversarial-Networks (GANs), ebenfalls unter Berücksichtigung von Suchanfrageänderungen und dynamischen Suchsitzungen.

Unsere Modellen können ein breites Spektrum kontinuierlicher Benutzerinteraktionen so simulieren [PR4, PR7], dass das Verhalten konsistent über eine Sitzung ist [PR6]. Die entwickelten Methoden haben wir im Open-Source-Softwareframework SimIIR 2.0 implementiert [PR6], das es auch anderen ermöglicht, realistische, koherente und konsistente Folgen von Benutzerinteraktionen mit Suchsystemen zu simulieren.

3 Project Development and Results

3.1 Project Goals

Learning from user interactions is pivotal in today's digital age, especially for platforms like search engines or digital libraries. Most online digital libraries, such as the Leibniz-Informationszentrum Wirtschaft (ZBW), enable users to submit queries, navigate through search results, and interact in various ways. Typically, users conduct searches in sessions. However, when a user modifies a query or interacts in an unanticipated manner, the system's response can be abrupt, causing a loss of context. It is a persistent challenge for digital libraries to discern users' search intent and to return the most appropriate results.

One of the main problems is that digital libraries typically do not have as many users to learn from as large search engines have. Our project's goal thus was to develop an open-source user simulation framework that supports assessing the effect of changes in a digital library's retrieval backend on users. The idea is to analyze the behavior of simulated users prior to actually changing the retrieval backend of a live production environment. The simulations ideally mimic real users' search behavior, the specific resources they would consult, and their potential follow-up decisions. By doing so, our project sought to enhance the data available for analyzing system performance, thereby complementing research studies on the analysis of real user query and interaction logs. The actual real search logs of a digital library, which contain basic information such as user IDs, timestamps, query strings, and clicked results, as well as detailed interactions like facet usage and other user interface activities, were instrumental in developing and refining our simulated user models. Our developed models can discern typical click-rank biases, follow query formulation strategies, and assess the realism of a simulation.

Our framework is designed to support a varied set of prototypical user models, each reflecting distinct click preferences, interaction patterns with system components, query reformulation habits, and search proficiency. A distinctive feature of our framework should be adaptability, allowing to customize user models to simulate a variety of backend retrieval scenarios and interaction dynamics. This adaptability extends to the creation of simulation models that mimic the conditions of real-world search environments, which might include variations in the lengths of result lists and the detail provided in search snippets.

The main goal was to establish an open-source simulation framework that supports the evaluation of a digital library's retrieval system through advanced, cost/gain-oriented simulated users. The ambition was to use this framework to deepen our understanding of user interactions with digital libraries and to inform development strategies. This would help to improve user satisfaction and system efficiency without necessitating premature system changes. Our research goals were to study and simulate the complexities and dynamics of search behavior in digital libraries, following a structured roadmap that led to interesting new insights and applicable tools. Our key findings can be categorized into three principal themes:

1. Applying a variety of models to imitate how users search and interact, including methods to align embedding spaces and user-simulation via Markov models.
2. Evaluating how authentic our different variants of simulated user behavior are.
3. Developing a software tool, the SimIIR 2.0 framework, to simulate search sessions based on Markov models and querying models obtained from log analyses.

To start, we examined log data, mainly using the Sowiport¹ User Search Session Data Set (SUSS)² [1] and data from the EconBiz search platform for economics and business studies, maintained by the project partner ZBW.³ We analyzed the data from different perspectives, applying established methods and also including resources like the user query variations (UQV) dataset [2]. Our models and findings are bundled in the open-source SimIIR 2.0 framework that received the best resource paper award at the conference CIKM 2022—a top-tier conference in the fields of information retrieval and knowledge management.

The next sections give more details on our results on understanding searcher behavior, the approaches we used, and the new tools we created in the project's work packages.

3.2 WP1 - Project Management and Dissemination

Goals: Project management, regular meetings, and the coordination of all dissemination activities.

Outcomes: We had regular virtual meetings with data contributors, researchers, and scientific supervisors / advisors. For short-term appointments and collaboration, we used Slack. Dissemination activities were mainly focused on publishing our results and the open-source simulation framework SimIIR 2.0 (cf. WP2). We had to refrain from publishing the usage data from the ZWB logs due to data privacy concerns. However, we always tried to demonstrate the validity of our results on public data from other sources.

3.3 WP2 - Format Specification and Framework Integration

Goals: Specification of simulation components, the interfaces between them, and selected retrieval systems; incl. configuration of a simulation pipeline and evaluation methods.

Outcomes: User interactions and search patterns are critical in understanding how people use search systems. We have started at analyzing the complexity of search patterns and developed a software tool that brings these insights together. This tool is especially useful for digital libraries, like ZBW, to simulate how their users might behave and to optimize the search systems towards the users' needs.

To capture fine-grained user interaction data and additional context data, a custom logging framework has been implemented in ZBW's production system. Specifically, user interactions have been captured on client side including specific data for the individual interaction elements (e.g., the rank of clicked items or which full text access options have been available to a user). In addition, we captured additional context data on the server side (e.g., all data related to the search results including the specific keywords-in-context snippets presented to the user, the specific facets, etc.). A data pipeline was implemented to cleanse, normalize and enrich the captured data and to monitor the data quality. The processed data is then provided to downstream components so that they can extract the necessary data as required.

For simulating search sessions utilizing this data, we started adopting the SimIIR framework [3], an IR simulation tool which was built to support experiments based on the so-called complex searcher model of search behavior. However, the SimIIR framework only provided a very rigid, declarative way for defining search behavior via pre-defined sets of rules—with a strong impact on usability and reproducibility. As a solution, we extended the original SimIIR framework and developed a new and improved version: SimIIR 2.0 [PR6] (see Fig. 1 for an overview).

SimIIR 2.0 is a substantial improvement that integrates new features to create simulations tailored to different kinds of users and their real behavior in logs of a real-world retrieval system. We integrate methods that use Markov models to get a more accurate picture of both general and individual user behavior (in our

¹<http://www.sowiport.de>

²The dataset is publicly available at <http://dx.doi.org/10.7802/1380>

³<https://zbw.eu/de/>

Figure 1: The architecture of our SimIIR 2.0 framework with components for the simulation of different user types.

log analyses, we have spotted two main kinds: 'exploratory searchers', who go through search results very thoroughly, and 'lookup searchers', who tend to check the first few results and then quickly change their search if needed). In addition, SimIIR 2.0 improves the flexibility of interactions between components, which enables for example to remember past interactions and use this history to influence future interactions. SimIIR 2.0 is publicly available as open-source software⁴ and has been awarded with the best resource paper award at CIKM 2022.

3.4 WP3 - Application Scenarios, Test Environment, and Evaluation

Goal: Application and evaluation of the simulation framework in realistic scenarios.

Outcome: Our project focused on the practical application and rigorous evaluation of the simulation framework in real-world scenarios of digital library environments. In WP3, we bridge the gap between theoretical models and their tangible utility in the context of user interaction within digital libraries.

To this end, we deployed the SimIIR 2.0 framework within the ZBW – the German National Library for Economics. This real-world setting provided us with a rich ground to apply and assess our simulation framework. The unique nature of digital libraries, characterized by specialized content and user objectives, offered an ideal scenario to observe and understand the intricate patterns of user interactions and search behavior. We constructed a dataset based on internal logs—not public for privacy reasons. The SimIIR 2.0 framework, with its advanced capabilities, served as a critical tool to simulate user interactions based on the ZBW data, thereby allowing us to closely examine how users navigate through, and engage with, the digital library's content.

An important aspect of WP3 was to establish a robust test environment. Besides the internal ZBW data, we also used the public User Search Session Data Set (SUSS) from the Sowiport digital library as it provides

⁴<https://github.com/padre-lab-eu/simiir-2>

a comprehensive view of user interactions. The SUSS data was instrumental to guide the development of our simulation models but also as a benchmark to evaluate their performance. By closely analyzing the data, we gained deeper insights into the nuances of search behavior, which were essential in refining our simulation approaches.

We evaluated our SimIIR 2.0 framework using methods developed in WP8. Our results indicate a high degree of similarity, validating the effectiveness of our simulation models. In addition, we performed an evaluation focusing on the relevance model provided by the framework, which determines whether a particular document is clicked or marked as relevant using an information need-specific/topical language model. The goal of this evaluation was to assess how reliably the simulation can predict whether editorial metrics such as nDCG@10 would improve or decline when comparing a new ranking variant to an existing baseline. This might be relevant, as this directional correctness could enable the evaluation of new rankers without relevance judgments as a use case for the simulation.

We based the evaluation on synthetic result lists, which were generated by selecting documents from a pool of pre-judged documents. These synthetic result lists were designed to have varying degrees of emphasis on the textual similarity to the query as well as the overall relevance of the documents across different simulation runs. For example, in some simulation runs the result lists had high overall relevance and less emphasis on the textual similarity, while in other runs the result lists had low overall relevance and high emphasis on the textual similarity. This allowed to assess across a diverse range of ranking conditions whether the behavioral metrics and the editorial metrics both improved or both declined when comparing two rankers. We used the information needs and the editorial judgments from the LibRank project.⁵

While predicting the direction of change in editorial metrics based on behavioral metrics such as number of clicks can be challenging when comparing arbitrary pairs of rankers, our results suggest this might become more feasible when the comparison is limited to rankers with a similar emphasis on textual similarity to the query. In practice, new rankers may frequently show a comparable level of textual relevance to existing baselines. So, in such cases, the simulation could potentially provide a sufficiently reliable proxy estimating the likely direction of change in editorial judgments, even when relevance judgments are unavailable. However, further research is needed to establish more robust guidelines for practitioners on the specific degree of change in behavioral metrics required for reliable predictions.

In conclusion, WP3 was instrumental in demonstrating the practical applicability of our research in a real-world digital library environment. The rigorous testing and evaluation methods employed ensured that our simulation framework was not only theoretically sound but also practically viable in enhancing the user experience in digital libraries. This work package laid a solid foundation for future advancements in the field, providing valuable insights that can be used to further refine digital library systems and the respective overall user search experience.

3.5 WP4 - User Interaction Models & WP6 - Artificial and Sample-based User Models

Goals: Models for user interaction behavior and generation of artificial data to extend real log data.

We combine the reports on WP4 and WP6, as they were intertwined through the use of Markov models.

Outcomes: A user search session contains a user's steps while searching in a digital library, which typically differs from behavior on general web search engines. Our goal is to understand and replicate how users behave. To create realistic simulations, we employed various techniques based on Markov models.

We started with a simple first-order Markov model that already did fit the data well, and then developed more complex models by adding conditions, context, time awareness, and considering changes in user

⁵<https://doi.org/10.7802/1253>

queries [PR1, PR2]. A crucial aspect of the research was examining dwell time, the duration between user actions. We estimated dwell time using a gamma distribution, enabling us to more accurately mimic user behavior. We assessed the accuracy of our simulation methods using the evaluation methods developed in WP8 and found that adding time-awareness to the Markov model made our simulations better, but just using some average time for dwell time did not work as well as the gamma distribution did. The study gave us a lot of useful information about how users search and interact in digital libraries, which can help make digital libraries more user-friendly.

The results also showed that our simulated sessions, particularly when we factored in the reasons behind query changes, mimicked real sessions very well. A trained classifier could hardly differentiate between the real and our simulated search sessions, which suggests that our simulations—for instance, the contextual Markov model—are sufficiently realistic.

Besides Markov models, we also explored the application of long short-term memory models (LSTM) to simulate search behavior. In particular, we analyzed whether an LSTM-based model can generate realistic user behavior data [PR5]. Trained on a cleaned version of the SUSS dataset (555,008 search sessions) [1], our LSTM model uses the whole session history to predict the next interaction. In an experimental analysis, we assessed the simulated sessions with respect to basic statistical characteristics (number of interactions, duration times, etc.), with respect to their plausibility in a human identification of real and simulated sessions, and with respect to their novelty compared to the training data (i.e., whether the LSTM model just “recites” memorized training sessions). Our results indicate that also LSTM-based session simulation is very promising from all three assessment angles.

3.6 WP5 - Query Formulation Models

Goals: Methods that simulate query (re-)formulation behavior.

Outcomes: In a pilot study [PR7], we assessed the applicability of search engine query suggestions to simulate search sessions (i.e., sequences of topically related queries). We automatically and manually evaluated to what extent a search session detection approach considers the simulated query suggestion-based sequences as “authentic” and we evaluated how humans perceive the session quality in the sense of coherence, realism, and representativeness of the underlying topic. As for the actual suggestion-based simulation, we used three different approaches for selecting the next query in a sequence based on Google’s query suggestions (other search engines are also possible): always selecting the first suggestion, random sampling, or topic-informed selection. We compared these suggestion-based session to the human sessions in TREC Session track data and to session in the Webis- SMC-12 dataset [4], as well as to a previously suggested three-word simulation scheme [5].

The results of our pilot study showed that it is easy to create suggestion-based search sessions that appear authentic to both users and automated evaluation, but that keeping the sessions related to an underlying topic can be difficult when relying on given suggestions only. We experimented with various combinations of suggestion selection strategies and desired session lengths. We identified issues in our strategies that are a direct result of the nature of search engine suggestions. The ‘first suggestion’ strategy is particularly prone to loops, when two queries are the top-ranked suggestions for each other—causing the generated session to alternate between two query strings; also observed for singular–plural pairs or categories (i.e., file formats, programming languages). To counter the looping issue, we then actually used a ‘unique query’ approach that ensures that queries are not repeated in loops within a session. Additionally, another policy ensures a minimum dissimilarity between consecutive queries—this helps to avoid plurals as top suggestions. However, while unique / dissimilar queries mitigate looping, we find that especially longer suggestion-based

sessions (say, ten queries) narrow down to very specific topics. A possible reason is that today’s search engine query suggestions do not only show related queries, but often offer more specific autocompletions. Still, as the suggestion-based simulations overall showed promising effects, we added suggestion-based query simulation as an option to the SimIIR 2.0 framework.

As another basis for simulated queries, we also experimented with anchor texts in the context of a Master’s thesis (Max Henze at MLU). The motivation was that most previous query simulators only combined keywords from the actual topics and from known relevant documents in rather simplistic ways. Instead, we evaluated simple and trained more sophisticated anchor text-based query simulators (e.g., language models on anchor text) and empirically demonstrated that anchor text-based simulated queries can form realistic sessions with respect to retrieval effectiveness and query authenticity. Since the results of the Master’s thesis came late in the SINIR project, we are trying to further improve and polish them for a potential conference paper submission after the project has ended.

3.7 WP7 - Meta-data Assessment from User Models

Goals: Methods to assess the query and interaction logs of real and simulated users.

Outcomes: When a user initiates a search with a specific query, the evolution of vocabulary in subsequent queries during a search session provides insights into the user’s intent and behavior. As part of our project, we analyzed this evolution of query vocabulary within search sessions [PR4].

A challenge we faced was the lack of comprehensive evaluation data that could simultaneously assess query vocabulary evolution and user interaction patterns. To address this limitation, we proposed a method that begins by mapping the query vocabulary into an embedding space, and then aligns the embedding spaces across different datasets. One dataset covers user interaction, while the other contains query and relevance judgments. We employed the Skip-thought model [6] combined with query vocabulary expansion. This involved learning a linear mapping function between pretrained word embeddings from Word2Vec and RNN word embeddings [7], extended further to use sent2vec for inducing query representations.

Our objective was to establish a mapping between a larger query embedding space \mathcal{V}_{s2v} (derived from a comprehensive query dataset) and the Skip-thought query embedding space \mathcal{V}_{ST} (trained on our specific query log sessions). This mapping was achieved using an unregularized L2 linear regression loss, enabling the translation of any query from \mathcal{V}_{s2v} to \mathcal{V}_{ST} .

Furthermore, we segmented user query sessions into consecutive query pairs (q_i, q_{i+1}) , creating two sub-datasets: D_1 containing source queries q_i , and D_2 containing target queries q_{i+1} . We then defined functions $f_1 : D_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d_1}$ and $f_2 : D_2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d_2}$ to map these subdatasets to their respective vector embedding spaces. This allowed us to establish a linear mapping function $A : \mathbb{R}^{d_1} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d_2}$, capturing the relationship between source query embeddings (initial queries) and target query embeddings (subsequent queries in the same session), such that $A(f_1(q_i)) \approx f_2(q_{i+1})$.

We then utilized this function to simulate new query pairs, providing insights into query reformulation patterns and vocabulary evolution within search sessions. This approach has the potential to enhance the user search experience by predicting likely query reformulations and adapting search results accordingly.

For modeling query embeddings, we used the User Query Variations (UQV) dataset.⁶ that illustrates the variety of ways different users could formulate queries around the same subject matter. While one user may have consistently used the same query, another might have explored up to ten different expressions for the same search intent.

For simulating user queries, our focus was on enabling the parameterization of query reformulation behavior,

⁶<https://culpepper.io/publications/robust-uqv.txt.gz> and <http://dx.doi.org/10.4225/49/5726E597B8376>

aiming for a representation that closely aligned with the actual evolution of search queries by real users. This involved simulating query sessions using various approaches and evaluating them with the sDCG measure. The results showed a direct correlation between the number of queries per session and the sDCG, suggesting that more queries in a session lead to a rapid increase in gain. Our methods were designed to offer a more detailed and accurate simulation of user interactions. A deeper understanding of query reformulation dynamics can lead to the optimization of search systems, thereby enhancing the user experience in finding relevant information. However, compared to the original plan, we mostly focused on query terms as vocabulary and less on metadata used, as datasets for conducting proper evaluation were missing.

3.8 WP8 - User-Model-based Evaluation and Quality Measures

Goal: Measures to interpret the performance of simulated users.

Outcomes: The study and assessment of user interactions within search sessions are crucial for enhancing digital libraries and other online platforms. Our study introduces a new method to assess the accuracy and realism of simulated user interactions, aiming to make them more closely resemble actual user behavior [PR3]. We utilized the User Search Session Data Set (SUSS) and implemented contextual Markov models to create these simulations. We then compared these simulated interactions with real user sessions using the two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, a statistical method that examines the similarities between two sets of data. Additionally, we employed a classification-based evaluation to further verify the accuracy of our simulated interactions.

Our study employed the two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS-2) goodness-of-fit test to compare two datasets, particularly to determine if two probability distributions are indistinguishable. The test involved calculating the absolute distance between the two data samples (test statistic d) to compare their distributions for similarities. We developed two separate simulation models for context-aware approaches to simulated users based on lookup or exploratory log subsets via Markov models that created user type-specific search sessions. Additionally, we trained a global simulation model trained on the entire dataset.

The evaluation of our simulation models involved both the Kolmogorov-Smirnov two-sample (KS-2) test and a classification-based approach. For the KS-2 test, we derived two separate simulation models (exploratory and lookup) and one global simulation model (first-order) trained on the entire dataset. We compared the transition probabilities between states from log sessions and simulated sessions for each model. The KS-2 test results showed that the statistical values (0.00417 for first-order, 0.00381 for exploratory, and 0.00302 for lookup) were smaller than the critical values (0.00421, 0.00389, and 0.00356 respectively) across all models. This led us to retain the null hypothesis, concluding that the simulated and real log sessions belong to the same distribution. However, since the KS-2 critical values were all significant, it was difficult to quantify the improvement using query change as a context factor through this test alone.

To further assess the realism of our simulation models, we implemented a classification-based evaluation. We developed features representing the sequentiality of user search sessions and trained classifiers to distinguish between simulated and real log data sessions. The classifiers included Support Vector Machine, Decision Trees (XGBoost), Random Forest, and Auto-sklearn. Results showed that the contextual Markov model (CMM) with the exploratory-lookup approach performed better, particularly for "Lookup" sessions (F-score of 0.519) compared to "Exploratory" sessions (F-score of 0.560). The lower precision, recall, and accuracy scores for the exploratory-lookup approach compared to the global first-order model indicated improved simulation quality. These findings suggest that grouping user search sessions based on behavioral characteristics enhances simulation quality, as evidenced by the reduced ability of classifiers to distinguish between real and simulated sessions.

In summary, our research presents a practical and cost-effective alternative to traditional user studies, demonstrating the potential of context-aware models. By enhancing the realism of our simulations, we gain deeper insights into user behavior, essential for developing more intuitive and efficient digital services.

3.9 WP9 - Learning To Rank Search Results from User-Models

Goal: Analyze a learning-to-rank approach that uses feedback from simulated users.

Outcomes: To study the effect of simulated data for learning-to-rank models, we experimented with pseudo queries and clicks simulated from Twitter data in the course of a Bachelor's thesis (Daniel Wächtler at MLU). As the simulation data, we exploited tweets that contain a link. We use a tweet's text as a simulated pseudo query and the link contained in the tweet as the pseudo click for that query.

In our experiments on Clueweb09, Robust04, und NFCorpus data, neural retrieval models learned better on the pseudo Twitter-based search interactions than classic retrieval models. Still, the neural models did not improve upon the retrieval effectiveness of the same models trained on non-simulated data. We had planned to run more experiments at the end of the project and in particular with queries and clicks simulated in different ways but the time did not suffice. Hence, further learning-to-rank experiments can still be a promising direction.

4 Publicly available project results

4.1 Peer-reviewed Publications

- [PR1] S. Zerhoubi, M. Granitzer, J. Schlötterer, and C. Seifert. "Query Change as a Contextual Markov Model for Simulating User Search Behaviour". In: *FIRE 2021: Forum for Information Retrieval Evaluation, Virtual Event, India, December 13 - 17, 2021*. Ed. by D. Ganguly, S. Gangopadhyay, M. Mitra, and P. Majumder. ACM, 2021, pp. 43–51.
- [PR2] S. Zerhoubi, M. Granitzer, C. Seifert, and J. Schlötterer. "Simulating User Interaction and Search Behaviour in Digital Libraries". In: *Proceedings of the 18th Italian Research Conference on Digital Libraries, Padua, Italy, February 24–25, 2022 (hybrid event)*. Ed. by G. M. D. Nunzio, B. Portelli, D. Redavid, and G. Silvello. Vol. 3160. CEUR Workshop Proceedings. CEUR-WS.org, 2022.
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- [PR4] S. Zerhoubi and M. Granitzer. "Simulating User Querying Behavior Using Embedding Space Alignment". In: *Linking Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries - 26th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries, TPD L 2022, Padua, Italy, September 20–23, 2022, Proceedings*. Ed. by G. Silvello, Ó. Corcho, P. Manghi, G. M. D. Nunzio, K. Golub, N. Ferro, and A. Poggi. Vol. 13541. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, 2022, pp. 386–394.
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- [PR7] S. Günther and M. Hagen. "Assessing Query Suggestions for Search Session Simulation". In: *Proceedings of the Causality in Search and Recommendation (CSR) and Simulation of Information Retrieval Evaluation (Sim4IR) Workshops at SIGIR 2021*. Ed. by K. Balog, X. Chen, X. Chen, D. Maxwell, P. Thomas, S. Zhang, Y. Zhang, and Y. Zhang. Vol. 2911. CEUR Workshop Proceedings. CEUR, 2021, p. 6.

4.2 Other results

- The source code of SIMIIR 2.0 and exemplary data is publicly available at [<https://github.com/padre-lab-eu/simiir-2>].

5 References

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